

Military Applications of Nuclear Power

“A Think Piece”

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I. Introduction

The nations' energy policy is again under review. Since President Carter's Administration, there have been as many energy initiatives as there have been Administrations. In each case, they strove to resolve long- and short-term energy issues, but at best they maintained an energy status quo. Consumers and environmentalists tolerated this in light of the relatively low price of crude oil and the appearance of a workable energy infrastructure. Unfortunately, this approach to energy policy merely delayed some of the very difficult decisions that must now be made.

Our energy policy is based upon an aging energy infrastructure: an antiquated energy distribution system; an electrical power grid network that was not designed to transfer power from one region to another [1]; limited fossil fuel, hydroelectric and alternate fuel reserves; and a public fear of nuclear power. As a result, the nation in 2001 faced rolling brownouts and blackouts; natural gas price increases of 50% from last year; and \$2/gallon gasoline...all this before 11 September 2001!

The Bush Administration must now develop a comprehensive, new energy policy, addressing not only short-term problems but also the more serious long-term problems. If a balanced approach is taken, there is a good chance things will improve, and this improvement will likely accelerate major changes in military power requirements in the 21st century.

The purpose of this article is to show what future military power requirements might be, how they are driven by fundamental changes in the nation's energy policy, and why nuclear power can solve those energy requirements. In particular, the article will describe how high-temperature, gas-cooled reactor technology can soon provide safe, efficient mobile power for most military needs.

Except for periods of worldwide recession, the days of \$1/gallon gasoline are probably gone forever. Whatever the U.S. does to improve the overall health of the energy policy, it will never be able to provide the public, private industry, or the military with fuel that cheap. The U.S. had enjoyed some of the lowest gasoline prices in the world for years. We were inundated with an almost unlimited supply of fossil fuels, and we wasted a lot of it because it

was so cheap (in many locations, natural gas is still burned off by refineries rather than used). But that was when the U.S. had its own reserves, and a relatively small number of countries were industrialized and slowly recovering from two world wars. Today, the burgeoning third world is poised to compete with the U.S. and other industrialized nations for the limited fossil fuel reserves, much of which happens to be controlled by OPEC. What we now see is the beginning of significant energy price increases, increases that could be fatal to our national economy if not properly addressed. The lynch pin of our energy policy is still the use of fossil fuels for most of the nation's energy needs. This reliance is becoming more difficult to support, since U.S. fossil fuel reserves are being used at an alarming rate.

The 21st century may well be remembered as the beginning of the worldwide transition from fossil fuels to what the authors believe will be the ultimate alternate fuel for transportation – hydrogen (H₂). The transition has already begun, and private industry is leading the way by developing prototype vehicles that use fuel cells and internal combustion engines that run on H₂ [2]-[4]. Hydrogen production, for both commercial and military applications, will have to increase in the decades to come as this transition proceeds. The authors further believe production facilities using nuclear energy will ultimately play a significant role in the emerging H₂ economy.

Utilities, businesses and developers have also expressed interest in fuel cells, which could make many homes and small businesses virtually independent of the electric power grid. Examples include: hospitals and other businesses that must keep operating when rolling blackouts are necessary during peak power usage, developing countries and rural communities, and other communities and regions with limited reserve power capacity and loath to build new power plants. Building a market for fuel cell generators in homes and businesses may spread the development cost of the technology beyond vehicles and accelerate consumer acceptance [4].

So what's the hurry? Fossil fuels still provide the world with approximately 80% (as of 1997) of their fuel requirements, and coal, oil and natural gas reserves are still being found throughout the world. The problem is the world population is rapidly increasing, depleting more rapidly the

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finite fossil fuel reserves while causing short-term and, some say, long-term environmental pollution. Let's look at each of these: world population, rapidly increasing energy consumption, and environmental pollution.

A. The World Population

By most measures, the earth is already overpopulated. "Humanity has already overshoot Earth's carrying capacity by a simple measure: no nation is supporting its present population on income – that is, the sustainable flow of renewable resources. Instead, key "renewable" resources, the natural capital of humanity, are being used so rapidly that they have become effectively nonrenewable" [5]. Even the U.S. must now rely upon other countries to support its current standard of living by importing additional foodstuffs, minerals and, of course, energy. An estimate of the increasing world population is shown in Fig. 1. It shows that world population will continue to increase for the next half century before leveling off at about 9 billion by 2055 [6].

Fig. 1. World Population Growth.

China has the largest population now, but a government-imposed birth control program (providing strong penalties to couples with more than one child) has already slowed its future growth. India, however, has yet to enact an effective birth control program. Thus, at the present population growth rate, India is expected to have the world's largest population by 2050.

Superimposed on this massive, third world population increase is the attempt of these countries to catch up with the industrial countries' standards of living. Such a rapid catch up can only occur with enormous expenditures of energy. The result is the civilian population will increase their per-person percentage of energy use.

B. Rapidly Increasing Energy Consumption

The 21st century was expected to be relatively peaceful, but that changed on 11 September. The specter of a nuclear world war involving many nations has been replaced with another kind of war: limited, regional warfare fueled by nationalism, religious fundamentalism, and perhaps overpopulation. To address the present worldwide asymmetric terrorist threat, one must first eliminate the political, economic, and military support structure and then turn toward improving global living standards, neither of which can occur without enormous increases in world energy consumption.

Right now, the U.S. consumes a greater percentage of the world's energy than any other country. In fact, the U.S. uses 25% of the world's total energy consumption each year, yet the U.S. population is just 4.6% of the world's 6 billion people. As the rest of the world (China, India, Brazil, etc.) demands more energy, the U.S. will have to compete for that energy. An increased demand for these limited fossil fuels means energy prices will increase even higher (see Fig. 2 [7]). Already, brownouts and blackouts are occurring more frequently, and unleaded regular gasoline has reached the psychologically significant \$2/gallon in California and Illinois...all this while known oil and natural gas reserves are relatively secure.

Fig. 2. World Energy Consumption by Region (1970-2020).

World oil reserves are difficult to estimate, and no one is certain how much recoverable oil is yet to be found. Nevertheless, the United States Geologic Survey World Energy Report has made a world oil reserve estimate of 1.6 trillion barrels of oil, a large percentage of this reserve is assumed to be heavy, sour crude oil. At the current rate of consumption, this reserve will be mostly depleted in 50 years [8]. Bahrain, one of the Arab Emirates, is predicting at the present rate of production they will exhaust their oil reserves in 12 years. Oil is not only the basis for gasoline and diesel fuels, it is also the feedstock for the plastics industry and an important raw material for the pharmaceutical and other industries. Burning up this valuable and irreplaceable resource as gasoline and diesel fuels is wasteful and shortsighted.

Complicating the oil supply further, over the last 20 years the number of oil refineries in the United States has declined substantially for a combination of economic, regulatory, and environmental reasons. Although advanced technologies may allow the capacity of existing refineries to expand marginally in the short term, it is unlikely that many new refineries will be located in the United States. This situation creates a long-term supply and economic security vulnerability. The United States currently consumes an average of 19.6 million barrels of oil per day, yet our refining capacity is 16.5 million barrels per day [8].

The picture is somewhat brighter in terms of available coal reserves. The United States has the world's largest proven coal reserves, about 275 billion short tons of recoverable coal. At the current consumption rate of slightly over 1 billion short tons per year, our reserves should last nearly 300 years. Burning coal has serious environmental consequences, however, and much of the U.S. coal re-

serves are of high sulfur coal, which current environmental regulations discourage burning [8].

The problem is further complicated by the fact that, even as our fuel consumption increases, our electrical transmission capacity is not keeping up. "Over the next ten years, U.S. demand for electric power is expected to increase by 25 percent, while transmission capacity is expected to increase by only 4 percent" [1]. It is estimated that 1300 new electrical generation plants will have to be constructed in the next 20 years to keep up with the projected demand [8].

C. Environmental Pollution

The fact that man exists in the environment means that man will change it. A small, environmentally conscious population will not make a significant impact on the environment in a short time. Of course the words small and short are relative terms, since a few hunters almost eliminated the entire U.S. bison population in the Western Plains in a few years. A relatively small population also rendered Dodos and passenger pigeons and numerous other flora and fauna extinct over a very short time frame. In the future, a few tourists could destroy the delicate balance on a coral reef or destroy the Asian lion and tiger populations. Such short-term impacts to the environment by just a few are well documented; what is less apparent is the long-term impact.

II. Alternate Energy Sources

As can be seen in Fig. 3 [9], the great preponderance of the world's energy supply is fossil fuel (approximately 80% as of 1997). Burning "renewable" fuels (wood and waste products) contributed another 11% of the total, but like fossil fuels, these combustion type energy sources contribute to atmospheric pollution such as so called "greenhouse gases". Sources of energy that don't contribute to atmospheric pollution make up only 9% of the total. Of this 9%, most hydroelectric sources have already been developed in the industrialized world, and solar, wind, and geothermal sources have serious technical drawbacks. There are no energy sources other than nuclear that can generate the world's long-term power requirements without causing atmospheric pollution.

Fig. 3. World Energy Supply.

Hydrogen is an environmentally attractive transportation fuel that has the potential to displace fossil fuels. It is a clean, sustainable resource with many potential applications, including generating electricity, heating homes and offices, making lower polluting gasoline and diesel fuels, and fueling surface and air transportation using fuel cells or internal combustion engines. Today, H₂ is produced primarily by steam reforming of natural gas, and is consumed primarily by chemical plants and petroleum refineries. For other applications requiring pure H₂, such as fuel cells, production is done by electrolysis. This is a relatively expensive process that uses electric current to dissociate, or split, water into its H₂ and oxygen (O₂) components. To achieve a viable H₂ economy, where H₂ demand is expected to increase by one or two orders of magnitude beyond current consumption rates, we must develop advanced technologies to produce H₂ at costs competitive with fossil fuels, using sustainable sources.

III. Nuclear Power

Nuclear power provides a safe and environmentally neutral power source that could efficiently produce the vast quantities of H₂ fuel required to support the increasing demand for fuel cell applications. The concept of using nuclear reactors with core temperatures between 750 and 1000 degrees Celsius (°C), combined with a thermochemical water splitting process, is probably the most economically feasible means of breaking down water into its component parts: H₂ and O₂. High-temperature, gas-cooled reactors (HTGRs) with coolant exit temperatures in this range, coupled with a system using thermochemical processes, could be used to produce bulk quantities of H₂. Waste heat from the nuclear reactor could be used for the desalination of seawater, removing the minerals and salts from seawater prior to passing it through the water splitting process or storing it as potable water for other uses.

Many types of thermochemical processes for H₂ production exist. The sulfuric acid processes (hydrogen sulfide, iodine-sulfur, and sulfuric acid-methanol) are leading candidates. In each of these processes, the high-temperature, low-pressure endothermic (heat-absorbing) reaction is the thermal decomposition of sulfuric acid to produce O₂. After O₂ separation, additional chemical reactions are required to produce H₂, typically requiring temperatures in the range of 800-1000 °C for efficient reactions. The leading candidate for thermochemical H₂ generation is the iodine-sulfur process, which uses an additional low-temperature step and an intermediate-temperature step to produce H₂ through chemical reactions [10].

(intermediate step)

The economics of H₂ production strongly depends on the efficiency of the method used. Hydrogen production by common electrolysis is relatively efficient (about 80 percent). But when combined with the required electrical conversion efficiency, which ranges from approximately 34 percent (in current light water reactors) to about 50 percent (for advanced systems), the overall efficiency of electrolysis is only about 25-40 percent. For thermochemical approaches such as the iodine-sulfur process combined with nuclear energy, an overall efficiency of greater than 50 percent is possible.

Burning coal or oil to generate electricity for production of H₂ by electrolysis would be wasteful and counterproductive by comparison. If the H₂ is produced using energy derived from fossil fuels, there is little or no economic or environmental advantage. Nuclear power plants, however, can provide safe, efficient, and clean power for converting large quantities of seawater into usable H₂ fuel and potable water. Such dual usage (H₂ fuel for equipment and potable water for human consumption) makes this an attractive concept, both for remote communities and military bases on a small scale as well as for regional production facilities on a larger scale.

For the military, a mobile nuclear power plant could be deployed as needed to remote theaters, where it could produce both H₂ fuel and potable water for use by U.S. and coalition forces in time of conflict. In peacetime, these same mobile plants could be deployed for humanitarian or disaster relief operations. These complementary roles make nuclear-generated supplies equally attractive to both military and civilian requirements, and this could foster joint programs to develop modern nuclear power sources for use in the 21st century.

IV. Military Applications

The military already has an extensive record of developing and using mobile nuclear reactors. They even had a program that considered the feasibility of using nuclear power plants to generate alternate fuels as a means of reducing logistics requirements for coal, oil, and gasoline. However, political, technical, and military considerations forced the closure of the program before a prototype could be built.

The Army Corps of Engineers ran a Nuclear Power Program from 1952 until 1979, primarily to supply electric power in remote areas. Stationary nuclear reactors built at Fort Belvoir, Virginia, and Fort Greely, Alaska, were operated successfully from the late 1950's to the early 1970's. Portable nuclear reactors were also operated at Sundance, Wyoming; Camp Century, Greenland; and McMurdo Sound, Antarctica. These small nuclear power plants provided electricity and steam heating for remote military facilities and could be operated efficiently for long periods without refueling [11].

In November 1963, an Army study submitted to the Department of Defense (DOD) proposed employing a military compact reactor (MCR) as the power source for a nuclear-powered energy depot, which was being consid-

ered as a means of producing synthetic fuels in a combat zone. While nuclear power could not supply energy directly to individual vehicles, the MCR could provide power to manufacture, under field conditions, a synthetic fuel as a substitute for conventional carbon-based fuels. The nuclear power plant would be combined with a fuel production system to convert water into H₂ fuel, which could then be used as a substitute for gasoline or diesel fuel in cars, trucks, and other vehicles.

By 1966, the practicality of the energy depot remained in doubt because of questions about the cost-effectiveness of its current and projected technology. Additionally, the Atomic Energy Commission (AEC), which supported the Army's efforts because they would contribute to the technology of both military and small commercial nuclear power plants, concluded that the probability of achieving the objectives of the Army program in a timely manner and at a reasonable cost was not high enough to justify continued funding. Cutbacks in military funding for long-range research and development because of the Vietnam War led the AEC to phase out its support. The costs of developing and producing compact nuclear power plants were simply so high they could only be justified if the reactor had a unique capability and met a clearly defined objective backed by the DOD. After that, the Army's Nuclear Power Program steadily declined and eventually stopped altogether.

The idea of using nuclear power to produce synthetic fuels, originally proposed in 1963, remains feasible today and is gaining significant attention because of recent advances in fuel cell technology, H₂ liquefaction, and H₂ transport and storage. Meanwhile, nuclear power has become a significant part of the energy supply in more than 20 countries - providing energy security, reducing air pollution, and cutting greenhouse gas emissions. The performance of the world's nuclear power plants has improved steadily and is at an all-time high. Assuming that nuclear power experiences further technological development and increased public acceptance as a safe and efficient energy source, its use will continue to grow.

Commercial, as well as military, demand for cost-effective chemical fuels such as H₂ is expected to grow rapidly. Fuel cell technology, which produces electricity from low-temperature oxidation of H₂ and yields water as the only by-product, is receiving increasing attention. As the commercial transportation sector increasingly moves toward H₂ fuel cells and other advanced engine concepts, DOD will eventually adopt this technology for its fleet of tactical vehicles and equipment. Using nuclear power to produce H₂, either at large central production facilities or at small remote facilities, offers the potential for a limitless chemical fuel supply with near-zero greenhouse gas emissions.

The demand for desalination of seawater is also likely to grow, as inadequate freshwater supplies become an urgent global concern. Potable water in the 21st century will be what oil was in the 20th century - a limited natural resource subject to intense international competition. In many areas of the world, rain is not always dependable

and ground water supplies are limited, exhausted, or contaminated. Such areas are likely to experience conflict among water-needy peoples, possibly prompting the deployment of U.S. ground forces for humanitarian relief, peacekeeping, or armed intervention. A mobile power plant could help prevent conflicts or provide emergency supplies of fuel and potable water to indigenous peoples and deployed ground forces.

V. New Nuclear Power Reactor Designs

Compact reactor concepts based on HTGR designs are attracting attention worldwide and could someday fulfill the role once envisioned for the military energy depot. One proposed design is the pebble bed modular reactor (PBMR) under development by the South African utility Eskom, the South African Industrial Development Corporation (IDC), British Nuclear Fuels Ltd., (BNFL) and the U.S. utility Exelon Corporation. A similar design is the gas turbine-modular helium reactor (GT-MHR) and remote site-modular helium reactor (RS-MHR) under joint development by General Atomics and the Russian Federation Ministry for Atomic Energy (MINATOM), and also sponsored by Japan and France.

The Modular HTGR concept originated in Germany in 1979, based on a Rankine cycle with steam conditions similar to fossil plants, but failed to demonstrate economic viability. Optimization studies in the 1990's indicated considerable cost savings using a closed-loop gas turbine (Brayton) cycle, compact heat exchangers, manufacturing and electronics. These differences introduce uncertainties and issues that must be addressed and resolved. If proven feasible, the HTGR technology could someday be used to replace retiring power plants, provide power for remote communities, expand the Navy's nuclear fleet, and provide mobile power for military or disaster relief operations. Ideally, modular power plants could be operated by a small staff of technicians and monitored by a central facility through a satellite uplink.

The technology of the HTGR designs features small, modular, helium-cooled reactors powered by ceramic-coated fuel particles capable of handling temperatures of 1,600°C that are inherently safe and cannot melt under any accident scenario. Limiting thermal power density and allowing sufficient heat losses from the reactor vessel can accomplish the key safety function of residual heat removal without the need for active safety systems. This approach results in simpler plant design and lower capital costs than existing light water reactors and proposed advanced designs. The PBMR and GT-MHR, coupled with a direct-cycle gas turbine generator, would have a thermal efficiency of about 42-45 percent and would produce about 110 megawatts of electricity (MWe) and 285 MWe, respectively. The smaller RS-MHR would produce about 10-25 MWe, which is sufficient for powering remote communities and military bases. Multiple modules can be installed on existing sites and refueling can be performed on-line, since the fuel pebbles recycle through the reactor continuously until they are expended and replaced. Both designs also feature coolant exit temperatures between 900°C and 950°C, high

enough to support efficient thermochemical water splitting cycles necessary for H₂ production.

For military applications, a small HTGR based on the RS-MHR design could be coupled to a thermochemical H₂ production facility, using the iodine-sulfur process or another of the chemical processes discussed earlier. Because the nuclear plant and the chemical plant would have significant inventories of hazardous materials, each must be isolated and protected from the other. This requirement would impose significant constraints on the plant, making any dual capability combining both electricity production by a turbine-generator and H₂ production by a chemical process unlikely. An energy depot would probably be a pure H₂ production facility, with waste heat from the reactor producing potable water primarily as the source supply for H₂ and the remainder available for human consumption.

There are many challenges to commercialization of an HTGR plant. The proposed gas turbine HTGR designs represent an advanced nuclear power concept that has not been demonstrated with an actual plant. Achieving successful deployment of this plant type will require careful development of the systems and components comprising the design, many of which are either new to the nuclear power industry, involve recent technological advancements, and/or consist of component applications operating in environments and configurations never before demonstrated. This is particularly evident with the gas turbine power conversion system components, where physical size, orientation and operating environment challenge the existing experience base. A proposed HTGR design coupled to a H₂ production system is even more speculative and will require extensive development, but should be compatible once the challenges to the gas turbine HTGR are resolved [12].

Assuming an HTGR plant based on the RS-MHR or similar design can be coupled to a thermochemical H₂ production facility, equipment could be transported inland by truck or railroad, or single modules could be built on vessels and deployed as needed to coastal regions. The Army's floating nuclear power plant on the barge Sturgis (Fig. 4, page 6), which provided electric power to the Panama Canal from the mid-1960s to the mid-1970s, demonstrated the feasibility of this concept. The compact RS-MHR reactor vessel measures approximately 3.4 m in diameter and 8.0 m high. The entire reactor and H₂ production system should be able to fit into two small pressure vessels contained within a shielded reactor building. Dimensions for a compatible H₂ production system, helium purification system, desalination system, and necessary connections and infrastructure are not defined, but the total plant may be expected to occupy at least 1300-1400 m³. This would be small enough for a mobile above-grade facility mounted on a single basemat or onboard a single ocean-going vessel.

Fig. 4. The MH-1A Sturgis Mobile Nuclear Power Plant Used a 45 MW Pressurized Water Reactor.

The efficiency of a large H_2 production facility is expected to be about 50 percent, with a 600 megawatts-thermal (MWt) reactor producing about 75 million standard (std) ft^3 of H_2 per day. For a 30-60 MWt RS-MHR plant, approximately 3-7 million std ft^3 /day could be expected. This output should meet the expected sustained energy demands of a deployed Task Force equipped with vehicles and other equipment powered by H_2 fuel cells or internal combustion engines.

VI. Implementation Steps

Nuclear power is expected to grow in the 21st century, with potential benefits applicable to military as well as commercial sectors. Small, modular nuclear power plants in mobile or portable configurations, coupled with H_2 production and desalination systems, could be used to produce H_2 fuel and potable water for military forces deployed in remote areas to reduce logistical requirements. Assuming the inevitability of H_2 fuel displacing fossil fuels, a clearly defined objective for developing a chemical fuel production capability now exists that was missing in 1966.

The Department of Energy (DOE), in its May 2001 report to Congress on Small Modular Nuclear Reactors, recognized the initial research into nuclear reactor technology and small reactors made by the U.S. Army in the 1950s and 1960s and showed that nuclear power facilities can be safely constructed and operated in remote areas. The former AEC's Power Reactor Development Program demonstrated that new reactor designs of small size could be constructed, tested, and placed on the electric power grid in a relatively short time frame (e.g., less than four years). The United Kingdom experience of applying a standardized gas-cooled reactor technology shows that HTGR designs can be expanded to provide a stable source of nuclear power in today's economic environment. However, the DOE report was made in response to Senate Report 106-395 to evaluate the feasibility of small nuclear power plants to provide electric power to remote areas and did not address the long-range feasibility of producing H_2 fuel.

The partnership between DOD and the former AEC to develop Army nuclear reactors contributed to the technology of both military and small commercial nuclear power plants for electricity generation. This historical relationship should be renewed to develop a prototype H_2 fuel pro-

duction capability using nuclear energy based on recent technological advances and projected logistical requirements, as well as projected increases in consumer demand for H_2 . DOD logistics planners should reconsider military applications of nuclear power and support ongoing DOE research and development initiatives to develop small modular nuclear reactors such as RS-MHR and others. For the Army to fight and win on tomorrow's distant battlefields, nuclear power will have to play a significant role, either directly or indirectly.

Would this necessarily lead to a rebirth of the old Army Nuclear Power Program, with soldiers trained as reactor operators and reactor facilities managed by the Corps of Engineers? Probably not. A more likely scenario would be a small fleet of nuclear power barges or other mobile power plant configurations developed by DOE, operated and maintained by Government technicians or civilian contractors, and deployed as necessary to support the Federal Emergency Management Agency, the Department of State, and DOD. Construction, licensing, refueling, and decommissioning issues could be managed under DOE stewardship and/or Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC) oversight. These and other issues would have to be addressed and resolved as research and development proceeds. As an end user of these proposed mobile nuclear reactors, however, the Army should understand their capabilities and limitations and provide designers with appropriate military requirements for their possible deployment to a combat zone.

VII. Conclusion

The days of cheap, seemingly inexhaustible supplies of fossil fuels are over. To flourish, national economies must be based on a more realistic energy policy. Whatever changes are implemented by this or by future Administrations must address both short-term changes to relieve immediate pressures and long-term changes to fix such fundamental problems as antiquated distribution and power grid systems. A look at the national policy and how it drives changes in the military shows the following:

- Improved global economies and an increasing global population will increase worldwide energy demand,
- Increased energy use will further deplete fossil fuel reserves and aggravate an already polluted global environment,
- The only viable alternative to fossil fuels as the ultimate energy source is seawater,
- Hydrogen derived from seawater is the ultimate fuel for mobile equipment,
- Nuclear power provides the most efficient, most environmentally neutral power for electricity generation as well as the production of H_2 fuel and potable water anywhere in the world,

- The military has years of experience with the development, operation and maintenance of transportable nuclear power plants,
- Recent nuclear reactor designs improve reactor safety and efficiency. In addition, some provide the necessary high temperature heat to generate commercial quantities of H₂, and
- DOD, DOE and the NRC must begin work now to look at ways to develop and deploy new, mobile nuclear power plant designs.

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